

Standing out in the third space

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TL;DR – If you don't want to read it all, please just go to the end – I'm asking us all to share something that we feel expresses our thoughts about third-space roles.

In my role as Head of Taught Students in the Institute for Academic Development, at The University of Edinburgh, I lead a team which provides support to ~45,000 UG and PGT students. This is very much a third-space role: I have to understand how students learn; how people teach; work on strategic initiatives; represent the student voice in decision making; and work across three Colleges and 21 Schools. In other words, it's a messy, complicated role. If I leave, I'm not sure how the University would work out what is required to replace me – and I suspect that is true of many third-space roles.

I no longer have as much direct student contact as I used to have, leading this area takes my time away from that. However, I do present at our Offer Holder events, and Pre-arrival/Welcome Week events. These are designed to give information, and offer time for students (and their parents/supporters) to ask questions. My main aim though is to be a welcoming presence, and to show that asking for support is not only normal, it is something that the happiest and most successful students feel able to do. As part of this I am often talking to very large groups, who may be hearing from lots of other support services or academic leads. Sometimes I am one of 15 presentations, and I am not vain enough to expect that the audience will all just remember what I say. I have taken to finishing my presentations with quotes, which are intended to either raise a laugh or make people think. My hope is that by doing something unexpected at the end, a memory of the support offered by my team may linger.

I have a range of quotations which I use. When talking to parents and supporters, I will often finish with:

"I may not have gone where I intended to go, but I think I have ended up where I needed to be" – Douglas Adams, The Long Dark Tea-time of the Soul

– which allows me to talk about how the journey belongs to the student, and it may end up not being what parents/supporters want or expect, but that's ok.

When talking to students I may end with:

"Do, or do not. There is no try" – Yoda, The Empire Strikes Back

– which allows me to tell students that I do want them to work hard, I do not want them to make studying the only thing they do, and I do want them to remember that my team is there to help them achieve their potential.

If I take this to the arena of third-space professionals, what quote might I use to help us all to express what it means to us?

I have used a Maya Angelou quote before:

“Success is liking yourself, liking what you do, and liking how you do it.” Maya Angelou

I use this quote with the caveat that Maya Angelou is one of the most mis-attributed authors of the twentieth century. However, I feel it explores one of the issues we face. How can we be confident about the value of our roles, and our skills? Universities can be a very hierarchical environment, and those hierarchies may have been established over a long period of time so seem insurmountable. In addition, our contribution may be harder to see: academic colleagues can point to their lectures, their research, the number of students they supervise because all of these are valued in the university environment. Yet, if a student cannot find resources in the Library, or cannot use the online learning environment, or isn't confident about revising for exams, they may have no capacity for their academic work. We cannot easily identify these more intangible things (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Identification

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/mikol/>“(System) FLEXIBILITY = COMPLEXITY” (CC BY-SA 2.0) by Mikol

I provided these instructions for the Slowposium participants, asking them to add thoughts, comments, quotes, pictures, sound clips etc., either anonymously or with name and institution provided.

I would like to ask people to think about how, or in what way, they would describe third-space roles, or the impact of these roles. It may be via a quote as I do; or a (very) short description; or an image, or a sound, or a metaphor whatever you want. I will then collate these, and try to draw out common themes, and highlight things which seem unique to circumstances, and write it up as a blog for the TELedvisors network. I'd hope that might kick off a longer discussion about our roles – if we can come up with some thoughts it could function a starting point for dialogue outside our sphere?

Thank you for your input, and I look forward to seeing what our community thinks.

The Slowposium ends on 30 November so that will be our deadline, and in honour of that allow me to finish with another quote:

“I love deadlines. I like the whooshing sound they make as they fly by.”

— Douglas Adams, *The Salmon of Doubt: Hitchhiking the Galaxy One Last Time*

Reflections after the Slowposium

One of the lovely things about the Slowposium was the opportunity to interact over a longer period of time than in a standard conference. There were really interesting contributions, from which I took away two themes.

Firstly the concept of transformation – both of us as individuals, but also the positive impact we have upon others, and our work environments. Articulating this can be challenging, and often it ends up with discussions on what our “outputs” are. This can reduce our work to what can be measured.

Secondly, the theme of working together was very important. This could be working as individuals within the third space, or bringing together groups and acting as a bridge, connecting people who might otherwise be in academic silos.

Both these themes relate to the issue of identity and visibility. More than a decade after Whitchurch (2013) gave us the language of “third space” we are still discussing how to explain our work, and often to justify it. Third space professionals are generally incredibly collegial and actively seek out opportunities to work in collaboration with others from across the sector. That is a strength, but one which is not always valued in Higher Education: for me, the question is how to make our way of working the gold standard in academic life.

Reference

Whitchurch, C. (2013). *Reconstructing identities in higher education: The rise of third space professionals*. Routledge.

About the author

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